

AN EXAMINATION OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS ACROSS DIFFERENT EDUCATIONAL LEVELS IN TERMS OF VARIOUS VARIABLES¹

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine school administrators working at different educational levels (primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools) in terms of several organizational and psychological variables. The research was conducted using a quantitative descriptive research design. The study sample consisted of 809 school administrators (169 primary, 196 lower secondary, and 444 upper secondary) drawn from the TALIS dataset. Data were collected using the School Climate Scale, School Crime and Violence Scale, Workload Stress Scale, Academic Pressure Scale, and Job Satisfaction Scale. To provide evidence for construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted separately for each school level. Reliability evidence was obtained using Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega coefficients. Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage), one-way ANOVA, and Spearman's rank-order correlation analyses were performed. The level of statistical significance was set at .05. Data analyses were conducted using SPSS 25 and JASP 0.16.1.0. Findings indicated that perceptions of school crime and violence frequency, workload stress, academic pressure, and job satisfaction differed significantly across school levels, whereas school climate perceptions did not show a statistically significant difference.

FARKLI OKUL KADEMELERİNDEKİ OKUL YÖNETİCİLERİNİN ÇEŞİTLİ DEĞİŞKENLERE GÖRE İNCELENMESİ

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Özet

Bu çalışmada, farklı okul kademelerinde (ilkokul, ortaokul, lise) görev yapan okul yöneticilerinin çeşitli değişkenlere göre incelenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Çalışma nicel araştırma yaklaşımlarından betimsel araştırma modeli ile yürütülmüştür. Araştırmanın evrenini Milli Eğitim Bakanlığına bağlı okullarda görev yapan yöneticiler oluştururken, örneklem TALIS verilerine dayalı olarak 809 okul yöneticisinden (169 ilkököl, 196 ortaokul, 444 lise) oluşmaktadır. Veriler; Okul İklimi, Okullarda Suç ve Şiddet, İş Yükü Stresi, Akademik Baskı ve İş Doyumu ölçekleri aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Her okul kademesi için doğrulayıcı faktör analizi yapılarak yapı geçerliğine, Cronbach alfa ve McDonald omega katsayıları hesaplanarak iç tutarlılığa ilişkin kanıtlar sunulmuştur. Veri analizinde frekans, yüzde, tek yönlü ANOVA ve Spearman sıra farkları korelasyon analizi kullanılmış; anlamlılık düzeyi .05 olarak belirlenmiştir. Analizler SPSS 25 ve JASP 0.16.1.0 programlarıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bulgulara göre okul iklimi algıları kademelere göre anlamlı farklılık göstermemiş; buna karşın suç ve şiddet sıklığı, iş yükü stresi, akademik baskı ve iş doyumunu düzeylerinin okul kademelerine göre anlamlı biçimde farklılaştığı belirlenmiştir.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An effective school fundamentally depends on the presence of effective school management. School administration is responsible for ensuring that schools achieve their legally defined goals, utilize human and material resources efficiently, and sustain a productive educational process (Gümüşeli, 1996a; Keser & Gedikoğlu, 2008; Demirtaş & Niyazi, 2014). Unlike other organizations, schools primarily focus on developing and transforming individuals, which renders their management both complex and critically important (Açıklın, 1995; Bursalıoğlu, 2000; Aslanargun, 2011). In this respect, the school principal emerges as a central determinant of school effectiveness, and research consistently underscores the pivotal role of leadership in school success (Balci, 1993; Demirtaş & Niyazi, 2014). Principals assume multifaceted responsibilities, including providing services to students and staff, overseeing curriculum implementation and development, strengthening school-community relations, and managing financial resources (Edward, 2000; Lashway, 2003; Vikki, 2003; Keser & Gedikoğlu, 2008). Therefore, the quality and effectiveness of the educational process are closely tied to the leadership competencies of school principals (Gürbüz et al., 2013).

Educational processes differ across levels of schooling, and these structural differences are reflected in centralized assessment systems. In Türkiye, students transition from primary to lower secondary education without a centralized examination; however, admission to upper secondary schools is determined through the High School Entrance System (LGS). Similarly, access to higher education depends on performance in the Higher Education Institutions Examination (YKS), including the Field Proficiency Tests (AYT). These differences in assessment structures and preparation processes justify the implementation of a tiered educational model. Accordingly, the Turkish National Education Basic Law No. 1739 defines level-specific objectives aligned with students' developmental characteristics, and the 4+4+4 education model has been adopted to enhance effectiveness and efficiency. Within this framework, school principals bear primary responsibility for implementing national legislation, curricula, and ministerial directives while ensuring that school goals are achieved (Şişman & Turan, 2004; Demirtaş et al., 2007).

As open systems, schools are influenced by numerous internal and external variables, which in turn affect school principals. Among these, incidents of crime and violence have become increasingly salient, reflecting broader societal trends (Akman, 2010; İkiz & Sağlam, 2017). Such incidents may directly increase principals' workload and contribute to occupational stress. Job stress has been shown to reduce productivity, impair interpersonal relationships, and negatively affect well-being (Yaşar, 2008; Yücel et al., 2019). Organizational stressors—including workload, job characteristics, working conditions, expectations, and concerns about the future—further intensify these pressures (Hatiboğlu & Radmard, 2014). At the same time, job satisfaction plays a crucial role in principals' professional well-being and overall quality of life (Avşaroğlu et al., 2005; Yücel et al., 2019).

Previous studies indicate that school management is shaped by contextual and structural factors such as school size, socioeconomic environment, institutional age, systemic challenges, globalization, and stakeholder relations (Gümüşeli, 2001; Demirtaş et al., 2007; Balyer, 2012; Hoşgörür & Orhan, 2017; Güneş & Esmer, 2018; Çetin, 2019). However, although these studies identify various determinants of school management, limited research has comparatively examined how key organizational and psychological variables differ across educational levels within a tiered education system. Understanding these differences is essential for developing level-sensitive management policies and practices.

Building on this theoretical and empirical background, the main research question of this study is formulated as follows:

Do school principals working at different educational levels differ significantly in terms of key organizational and psychological variables?

Within the scope of this overarching question, the following sub-questions are addressed:

1. Is there a statistically significant difference between school level and principals' perceptions of school climate?
2. Is there a statistically significant difference between school level and the frequency of crime and violence in schools as perceived by principals?
3. Is there a statistically significant difference between school level and principals' workload stress levels?
4. Is there a statistically significant difference between school level and principals' perceived academic pressure?
5. Is there a statistically significant difference between school level and principals' job satisfaction levels?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Model

The present study aimed to examine school principals working at different educational levels in terms of various organizational and psychological variables. In line with this purpose, a quantitative research approach was adopted, and the study was conducted using a descriptive research design (Şata, 2020). Descriptive research designs are primarily concerned with identifying, describing, and interpreting existing conditions without manipulating variables. Such designs aim to portray the current status of phenomena as they naturally occur, often through the use of large and representative samples. In this context, descriptive studies enable researchers to systematically examine differences, relationships, and patterns across groups based on predefined variables. Rather than establishing causal inferences, this approach focuses on providing an accurate and comprehensive picture of the situation under investigation. Accordingly, this study seeks to present a structured and data-driven description of how selected variables differ across school levels, thereby contributing to a clearer understanding of school management dynamics within a tiered education system.

2.2. Population and Sample

The data for this study were derived from the TALIS 2018 dataset. The population of the study consisted of school principals working in primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education. The sample comprised 828 principals (primary = 173, lower secondary = 198, upper secondary = 457) selected through stratified random sampling, one of the probability sampling methods. During the data screening and cleaning process, some cases were identified as containing missing data and were therefore excluded from the analysis. Analysis of the 19 excluded cases indicated that the missing data were Missing Completely at Random (MCAR); therefore, listwise deletion was applied in subsequent analyses. As a result, the final sample included 809 school principals (primary = 169, lower secondary = 196, upper secondary = 444). Descriptive statistics regarding the socio-demographic characteristics of the participating principals are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Frequencies and Percentages of School Principals' Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Variables		f	%
Gender	Female	59	7.3
	Male	748	92.5
	Missing	2	0.2
Level of education	Associate Degree	20	2.5
	Bachelor's Degree	554	68.5
	Master's Degree	231	28.5
	Doctoral Degree	4	0.5
School level	Primary	169	20.9
	Lower Secondary	196	24.2
	Upper Secondary	444	54.9
Okulun bulunduğu yerleşim yeri	Village	80	9.9
	Town	47	5.8
	District	192	23.7
	Province	257	31.8
	Metropolitan city	226	27.9
	Missing	7	0.9
Total		809	100

When Table 1 is examined, it is observed that the majority of school principals are male and hold a bachelor's degree. Regarding the distribution by school level, most of the participants are principals working in upper secondary schools. In terms of school location, the number of schools located in villages is comparatively lower, while the frequencies across other types of settlements appear to be relatively similar.

2.3. Data Collection Tool

In line with the purpose of the study, data collection instruments developed by the OECD and administered within the scope of TALIS 2018 were utilized (Ceylan et al., 2020). Given that this research aimed to examine school principals working at different educational levels in terms of various organizational and psychological variables, five distinct scales were employed. The variables considered in the study were identified as school climate, frequency of crime and violence in schools, principals' job satisfaction levels, principals' workload stress levels, and principals' perceived academic pressure. Detailed information regarding the data collection instruments used to measure each variable is presented below.

2.3.1. School climate scale

The School Climate Scale developed by the OECD (2019) was used to determine principals' perceptions of the school climate in their respective schools. The scale consists of 11 items (e.g., "This school provides staff with opportunities to actively participate in school decision-making"), is structured as a four-point Likert-type scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 4 = Strongly agree), and has a unidimensional structure. Although the OECD provided evidence for the validity and reliability of the measurement instrument based only on lower secondary school data, the present study included all educational levels; therefore, validity and reliability analyses were re-examined separately for each school level. To provide evidence for construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted for each educational level. To establish reliability, internal consistency coefficients—Cronbach's alpha (α) and McDonald's omega (ω)—were calculated. The results of the validity and reliability analyses for the School Climate Scale are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Validity and reliability analyses of the school climate scale

	Fit values	Primary	Secondary	Highschool
Validity	χ^2/df	1.466	0.643	2.994
	CFI	.982	1.000	.965
	NNFI	.978	1.000	.956
	NFI	.946	.966	.948
	RMSEA	.053	.000	.067
	SRMR	.101	.076	.090
	GFI	.964	.980	.969
Reliability	Cronbach α	.849	.861	.839
	McDonald ω	.873	.874	.856

Table 2 presents the validity and reliability evidence of the School Climate Scale across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary school levels. Regarding construct validity, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results indicate acceptable to good model fit across all three levels. The χ^2/df ratios were 1.466 for primary schools, 0.643 for lower secondary schools, and 2.994 for upper secondary schools, all within acceptable thresholds. Comparative fit indices were high across groups (CFI = .982, 1.000, and .965; NNFI = .978, 1.000, and .956; NFI = .946, .966, and .948 for primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools, respectively), indicating strong model fit. RMSEA values (.053, .000, and .067) suggest good to acceptable fit, while SRMR values (.101, .076, and .090) fall within acceptable ranges. GFI values (.964, .980, and .969) further support the adequacy of the model across all school levels. In terms of reliability, the internal consistency coefficients demonstrate satisfactory levels across groups. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were .849 (primary), .861 (lower secondary), and .839 (upper secondary), while McDonald's omega coefficients were .873, .874, and .856, respectively. These findings indicate that the scale provides reliable measurements at each educational level.

2.3.2. Frequency of crime and violence in schools scale

The Frequency of Crime and Violence in Schools Scale is a unidimensional instrument consisting of four items (e.g., "Physical injury caused by violence among students") and is rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Never, 5 = Every day). The scale is designed to measure the perceived frequency of crime and violent incidents occurring within schools. Since the validity and reliability analyses conducted by the OECD were limited to a single school level, these analyses were re-examined separately for all three educational levels in the present study. The estimation results obtained from the validity and reliability analyses are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Validity and reliability analyses of the frequency of crime and violence in schools scale

	Fit values	Primary	Secondary	Highschool
Validity	χ^2/df	0.634	1.480	4.479
	CFI	1.000	.997	.990
	NNFI	1.000	.992	.970
	NFI	.999	.992	.987
	RMSEA	.000	.049	.089
	SRMR	.011	.016	.020
	GFI	1.000	.992	.990
Reliability	Cronbach α	.832	.857	.836
	McDonald ω	.858	.871	.845

Table 3 presents the validity and reliability findings for the Frequency of Crime and Violence in Schools Scale across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary school levels. With respect to construct validity, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results indicate good to acceptable model fit across the three school levels. The χ^2/df ratios were 0.634 for primary schools, 1.480 for lower secondary schools, and 4.479 for upper secondary schools. Comparative fit indices were high for all groups (CFI = 1.000, .997, and .990; NNFI = 1.000, .992, and .970; NFI = .999, .992, and .987 for primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools, respectively), suggesting strong model fit. RMSEA values were .000 for primary, .049 for lower secondary, and .089 for upper secondary schools, indicating excellent fit for primary, good fit for lower secondary, and acceptable fit for upper secondary schools. SRMR values (.011, .016, and .020) further support good model fit across all levels. Additionally, GFI values (1.000, .992, and .990) demonstrate very good overall fit. Regarding reliability, internal consistency coefficients were satisfactory across all educational levels. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were .832 (primary), .857 (lower secondary), and .836 (upper secondary), while McDonald's omega coefficients were .858, .871, and .845, respectively. These results indicate that the scale demonstrates adequate internal consistency at each school level.

2.3.3. Workload stress scale

The Workload Stress Scale was developed to measure school principals' perceived workload-related stress in the schools where they serve (OECD, 2019). The instrument consists of six items (e.g., "Having additional duties when teachers are absent") and is rated on a four-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 4 = Strongly agree). The scale has a unidimensional structure. Evidence regarding the validity and reliability of the measurements obtained from the scale is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Validity and reliability analyses of the workload stress scale

	Fit values	Primary	Secondary	Highschool
Validity	χ^2/df	1.633	2.651	3.376
	CFI	.969	.944	.963
	NNFI	.949	.907	.939
	NFI	.927	.915	.949
	RMSEA	.061	.092	.073
	SRMR	.040	.049	.037
	GFI	.983	.964	.978
Reliability	Cronbach α	.747	.772	.767
	McDonald ω	.758	.786	.785

Table 4 presents the validity and reliability results for the Workload Stress Scale across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary school levels. Regarding construct validity, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results indicate acceptable model fit across all three school levels. The χ^2/df ratios were 1.633 for primary schools, 2.651 for lower secondary schools, and 3.376 for upper secondary schools, all within acceptable limits. Comparative fit indices were satisfactory (CFI = .969, .944, and .963; NNFI = .949, .907, and .939; NFI = .927, .915, and .949 for primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools, respectively). RMSEA values were .061 for primary, .092 for lower secondary, and .073 for upper secondary schools, indicating good fit for primary and upper secondary levels and acceptable fit for lower secondary schools. SRMR values (.040, .049, and .037) fall within acceptable thresholds, and GFI values (.983, .964, and .978) further support adequate model fit. In terms of reliability, the internal consistency coefficients demonstrate acceptable levels across school levels. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were

.747 (primary), .772 (lower secondary), and .767 (upper secondary), while McDonald's omega coefficients were .758, .786, and .785, respectively. These values indicate that the scale yields reliable measurements across all three educational levels.

2.3.4. Academic pressure scale

The Academic Pressure Scale was developed to determine the level of pressure arising from academic expectations in the schools where principals serve. The instrument consists of seven items (e.g., "Teachers have high expectations for student achievement") and is rated on a four-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 4 = Strongly agree). The scale demonstrates a unidimensional structure. Evidence regarding the validity and reliability of the measurements obtained from the instrument was collected, and the results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Validity and reliability analyses of the academic pressure scale

	Fit values	Primary	Secondary	Highschool
Validity	χ^2/df	1.651	2.790	4.545
	CFI	.990	.954	.967
	NNFI	.986	.931	.951
	NFI	.976	.931	.959
	RMSEA	.062	.096	.089
	SRMR	.073	.109	.081
	GFI	.988	.974	.983
Reliability	Cronbach α	.883	.821	.837
	McDonald ω	.887	.825	.841

Table 5 presents the validity and reliability results for the Academic Pressure Scale across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary school levels. Regarding construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results indicate acceptable to good model fit across the three school levels. The χ^2/df ratios were 1.651 for primary schools, 2.790 for lower secondary schools, and 4.545 for upper secondary schools. Comparative fit indices were high (CFI = .990, .954, and .967; NNFI = .986, .931, and .951; NFI = .976, .931, and .959 for primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools, respectively), supporting adequate model fit. RMSEA values were .062 for primary, .096 for lower secondary, and .089 for upper secondary schools, indicating good fit for primary schools and acceptable fit for lower secondary and upper secondary schools. SRMR values (.073, .109, and .081) were within acceptable limits for primary and upper secondary schools, while slightly higher for lower secondary schools. GFI values (.988, .974, and .983) further demonstrate strong overall fit across all levels. In terms of reliability, internal consistency coefficients were satisfactory across school levels. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were .883 (primary), .821 (lower secondary), and .837 (upper secondary), while McDonald's omega coefficients were .887, .825, and .841, respectively. These findings indicate that the Academic Pressure Scale demonstrates adequate internal consistency across all educational levels.

2.3.5. Job satisfaction scale

The Job Satisfaction Scale was developed to determine school principals' perceptions of job satisfaction regarding their profession. The instrument consists of 10 items, three of which are reverse-coded (e.g., "The advantages of this profession clearly outweigh its disadvantages"), and is rated on a four-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 4 = Strongly agree). The scale has a unidimensional structure. Evidence regarding the validity and reliability of the measurements obtained from the instrument was collected, and the results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Validity and reliability analyses of the job satisfaction scale

	Fit values	Primary	Secondary	Highschool
Validity	χ^2/df	1.481	1.961	2.280
	CFI	.965	.937	.964
	NNFI	.954	.920	.954
	NFI	.900	.882	.938
	RMSEA	.054	.070	.054
	SRMR	.088	.091	.068
	GFI	.951	.917	.977
Reliability	Cronbach α	.783	.751	.792
	McDonald ω	.791	.757	.792

Table 6 presents the validity and reliability results for the Job Satisfaction Scale across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary school levels. Regarding construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results indicate acceptable model fit across all three educational levels. The χ^2/df ratios were 1.481 for primary schools, 1.961 for lower secondary schools, and 2.280 for upper secondary schools, all within acceptable limits. Comparative fit indices were satisfactory (CFI = .965, .937, and .964; NNFI = .954, .920, and .954; NFI = .900, .882, and .938 for primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools, respectively). RMSEA values (.054, .070, and .054) indicate good fit for primary and upper secondary schools and acceptable fit for lower secondary schools. SRMR values (.088, .091, and .068) fall within acceptable ranges. Additionally, GFI values (.951, .917, and .977) further support adequate model fit across school levels. In terms of reliability, internal consistency coefficients were acceptable across groups. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were .783 (primary), .751 (lower secondary), and .792 (upper secondary), while McDonald's omega coefficients were .791, .757, and .792, respectively. These findings indicate that the scale demonstrates satisfactory internal consistency across all educational levels.

2.4. Data Analysis

In the data analysis process, several statistical techniques were employed in a sequential and systematic manner. First, descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were calculated to summarize the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants and to provide an overview of the distribution of variables. Subsequently, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to examine whether there were statistically significant differences across school levels with respect to the variables under investigation. To establish evidence for construct validity of the measurement instruments, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed separately for each educational level. Internal consistency reliability of the scales was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega coefficients. In addition, Spearman's rank-order correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships among the study variables.

The level of statistical significance was set at .05 for all analyses. Data analyses were carried out using SPSS (Version 25) and JASP (Version 0.16.1.0) statistical software packages.

3. FINDINGS

In this section, the findings obtained in line with the purpose of the study are presented. First, descriptive statistics of the measurements obtained from the instruments are reported

separately for each educational level. The descriptive statistics of the measurements derived from the instruments for the school level are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Descriptive statistics of the measurements obtained from the instruments for the school level

School	Measures	n	Min.	Max.	\bar{X}	SD	Skew.	Kurt.
Primary	School Climate	169	20.00	44.00	34.85 (3.17)	4.24	-0.32	0.37
	Frequency of Crime and Violence	169	4.00	17.00	6.70 (1.68)	2.81	1.43	1.85
	Workload Stress	169	6.00	24.00	12.51 (2.09)	3.49	0.71	0.66
	Academic Pressure	169	13.00	28.00	21.41 (3.06)	3.85	0.06	-0.69
	Job Satisfaction	169	14.00	40.00	30.10 (3.01)	4.86	-0.37	0.12
Secondary	School Climate	196	11.00	44.00	33.95 (3.09)	4.28	-0.61	4.27
	Frequency of Crime and Violence	196	4.00	20.00	7.86 (1.97)	3.35	1.14	1.17
	Workload Stress	196	6.00	24.00	13.48 (2.24)	3.55	0.28	0.16
	Academic Pressure	196	13.00	28.00	20.35 (2.91)	3.28	0.38	0.05
	Job Satisfaction	196	16.00	39.00	29.38 (2.94)	4.61	-0.23	-0.41
Highschool	School Climate	444	11.00	44.00	34.03 (3.09)	4.15	-0.33	2.17
	Frequency of Crime and Violence	444	3.88	19.00	6.13 (1.53)	2.43	1.92	5.34
	Workload Stress	444	6.00	24.00	12.89 (2.15)	3.38	0.32	0.19
	Academic Pressure	444	9.00	28.00	19.62 (2.80)	3.65	0.30	-0.22
	Job Satisfaction	444	10.00	40.00	30.70 (3.07)	4.66	-0.40	0.62

Note: Values in parentheses represent item-level mean scores calculated by dividing the total scale score by the number of items.

Table 7 presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables across primary (n = 169), lower secondary (n = 196), and upper secondary (n = 444) school levels. For primary schools, the mean scores were 34.85 (SD = 4.24) for school climate, 6.70 (SD = 2.81) for frequency of crime and violence, 12.51 (SD = 3.49) for workload stress, 21.41 (SD = 3.85) for academic pressure, and 30.10 (SD = 4.86) for job satisfaction. Skewness and kurtosis values indicate generally acceptable normality, although crime and violence showed moderate positive skewness (1.43). For lower secondary schools, the mean scores were 33.95 (SD = 4.28) for school climate, 7.86 (SD = 3.35) for crime and violence, 13.48 (SD = 3.55) for workload stress, 20.35 (SD = 3.28) for academic pressure, and 29.38 (SD = 4.61) for job satisfaction. The distributions were generally close to normal, though school climate demonstrated higher kurtosis (4.27). For upper secondary schools, the mean scores were 34.03 (SD = 4.15) for school climate, 6.13 (SD = 2.43) for crime and violence, 12.89 (SD = 3.38) for workload stress, 19.62 (SD = 3.65) for academic pressure, and 30.70 (SD = 4.66) for job satisfaction. Crime and violence exhibited higher skewness (1.92) and kurtosis (5.34), indicating a more positively skewed and peaked distribution compared to other variables.

Table 8. One-Way ANOVA results comparing variables across school levels.

Variable	Primary ¹ (n=169)M (SD)	Secondary ² (n=196) M (SD)	High School ³ (n=444) M (SD)	F	p	η^2	Post-Hoc (Bonferroni)
School Climate	34.85 (4.24)	33.95 (4.28)	34.03 (4.15)	2.70	.068	.007	n.s.
Frequency of Crime & Violence	6.70 (2.81)	7.86 (3.35)	6.13 (2.43)	26.73	.000	.062	2 > 1, 2 > 3
Workload Stress	12.51 (3.49)	13.48 (3.55)	12.89 (3.38)	3.80	.023	.009	2 > 1
Academic Pressure	21.41 (3.85)	20.35 (3.28)	19.62 (3.65)	15.43	.000	.037	1 > 2; 3, 2 > 3
Job Satisfaction	30.10 (4.86)	29.38 (4.61)	30.70 (4.66)	5.46	.004	.013	3 > 2

Note: Effect sizes are reported using eta squared (η^2). Levene's test indicated that the assumption of homogeneity of variances was met for all variables (p > .05).

A one-way ANOVA revealed that school climate perceptions did not differ significantly across school levels, $F(2, 806) = 2.70, p = .068$. Although primary school principals (M = 34.85, SD

= 4.24) reported slightly higher perceptions than secondary ($M = 33.95, SD = 4.28$) and high school principals ($M = 34.03, SD = 4.15$), these differences were not statistically significant. Thus, school level does not appear to be a determining factor in principals' perceptions of school climate.

There was a statistically significant difference in the frequency of crime and violence across school levels, $F(2, 806) = 26.73, p < .001$. Post-hoc comparisons indicated that secondary school principals ($M = 7.86, SD = 3.35$) reported significantly higher levels than both primary ($M = 6.70, SD = 2.81$) and high school principals ($M = 6.13, SD = 2.43$). No significant difference was observed between primary and high schools. These findings suggest that perceived crime and violence are more prevalent in lower secondary school contexts.

A significant difference was found in principals' workload stress levels across school levels, $F(2, 806) = 3.80, p = .023$. Post-hoc analysis showed that secondary school principals ($M = 13.48, SD = 3.55$) reported significantly higher workload stress compared to primary school principals ($M = 12.51, SD = 3.49$). Differences involving high school principals ($M = 12.89, SD = 3.38$) were not statistically significant. This finding indicates that workload-related stress is particularly pronounced at the lower secondary level.

The analysis revealed a significant difference in perceived academic pressure across school levels, $F(2, 806) = 15.43, p < .001$. Post-hoc results indicated that primary school principals ($M = 21.41, SD = 3.85$) reported significantly higher academic pressure than both secondary ($M = 20.35, SD = 3.28$) and high school principals ($M = 19.62, SD = 3.65$). Additionally, secondary school principals reported significantly higher academic pressure than high school principals. These findings suggest a decreasing trend in perceived academic pressure from primary to upper secondary levels.

A statistically significant difference was found in job satisfaction across school levels, $F(2, 806) = 5.46, p = .004$. Post-hoc comparisons indicated that high school principals ($M = 30.70, SD = 4.66$) reported significantly higher job satisfaction than secondary school principals ($M = 29.38, SD = 4.61$). No other pairwise differences were statistically significant. This suggests that job satisfaction levels are relatively higher among high school principals compared to those working in lower secondary schools.

The ANOVA results revealed varying levels of effect sizes across school levels. The effect size for school climate was negligible ($\eta^2 = .007$), indicating that school level had a minimal influence on this variable. For frequency of crime and violence, the effect size was moderate ($\eta^2 = .062$), suggesting a meaningful and practically significant impact of school level. The effect size for workload stress was small ($\eta^2 = .009$). Academic pressure demonstrated a small-to-moderate effect ($\eta^2 = .037$), indicating a limited but noteworthy influence of school level. Finally, job satisfaction yielded a small effect size ($\eta^2 = .013$). Overall, the strongest effect was observed for the frequency of crime and violence variable.

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicate that school climate perceptions were high across all educational levels according to principals' evaluations. Moreover, school climate did not differ significantly across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary levels. This suggests that principals, regardless of school level, perceive the organizational atmosphere of their schools in a similar and generally positive manner. Although no prior study directly examining principals' school climate perceptions by school level was identified, previous research has documented significant differences in school climate perceptions among teachers, students, and parents across levels (Güzelgörüç et al., 2021; Şahin & Atbaşı, 2020). For instance, Özgenel and Bozkurt (2020) reported higher levels of perceived school happiness among primary school teachers compared to those working in lower secondary and upper secondary schools. Similarly, Cavrini et al. (2015) and Altuntaş et al. (2020) found that parents of primary school students reported more positive academic and social climate perceptions than parents of secondary school students. Karaman and

Yurtal (2015) also reported that students in lower grades had more positive school climate perceptions compared to those in upper grades.

While these studies suggest that school climate tends to vary across educational levels, the present study did not find such differences among principals. This unexpected finding may indicate that principals, irrespective of school level, actively strive to maintain a positive school climate within their institutions. Given the documented positive relationship between school climate and academic achievement (Bahçetepe & Giorgetti, 2015; Karadağ et al., 2016; Macneil et al., 2009; Neibuhr, 1995), principals' consistent perceptions may reflect a shared managerial emphasis on sustaining environments conducive to learning.

Regarding the frequency of crime and violence, although overall levels were reported as very low across all school levels, significant differences emerged. Lower secondary principals reported significantly higher levels of crime and violence compared to both primary and upper secondary principals. Although Demirtaş et al. (2007) found that problem frequency was higher in upper secondary schools, other studies suggest that violence and behavioral problems vary by developmental stage. İkiz and Sağlam (2017) found that lower school attachment was associated with increased violence and that eighth-grade students displayed higher tendencies toward violence compared to other lower secondary grades. Hoşgörür and Orhan (2017) reported that violence and bullying had extended even to primary levels. Given that lower secondary students (approximately ages 10–14) are in a transitional developmental period between childhood and adolescence, the heightened levels reported in this study may be linked to developmental instability and identity formation processes.

With respect to workload stress, principals across all levels reported low levels overall; however, lower secondary principals experienced significantly higher stress than primary school principals. Previous research has identified financial constraints, stakeholder relations, administrative challenges, and physical conditions as stress-inducing factors for school leaders (Güneş & Esmer, 2018; Çetin, 2019). The elevated stress levels among lower secondary principals may be attributed to the complexity of managing multiple subject teachers, transitional student adjustment processes, and preparation for the High School Entrance System (LGS), which imposes additional administrative and academic responsibilities.

Academic pressure was found to be high across all school levels, with primary school principals reporting the highest levels, followed by lower secondary and upper secondary principals. This finding may reflect the foundational role of primary education in shaping students' academic trajectories. Ensuring strong academic foundations at the primary level may generate heightened accountability pressures for principals. Although it might be expected that upper secondary principals would experience greater pressure due to high-stakes examinations such as YKS and AYT, the findings suggest that early academic accountability and foundational performance expectations may exert stronger perceived pressure at earlier educational stages.

The findings of the present study indicate that academic pressure is highest at the primary school level (primary > secondary > high school). Within the context of the Turkish education system, this result can be explained by the strong emphasis placed on establishing foundational academic skills during the early years of schooling. In Türkiye, expectations regarding students' academic achievement are heavily emphasized by both parents and teachers from an early age. Particularly during primary education, where basic literacy and numeracy skills are developed,

a performance-oriented approach may be adopted to prepare students for subsequent educational stages.

Additionally, high parental expectations and the competitive nature of the education system may contribute to increased perceptions of academic pressure at the primary level. In contrast, at the secondary and high school levels, students may develop greater familiarity with academic processes and assessment systems, which could lead to a relatively lower perception of pressure. This finding highlights the need to reconsider the academic demands placed on students in early education and offers important implications for educational policy and practice in Türkiye.

Finally, job satisfaction levels were high across all school levels, with upper secondary principals reporting significantly higher satisfaction than lower secondary principals. This indicates that despite encountering various organizational challenges, principals generally derive professional fulfillment from their roles. The higher satisfaction levels among upper secondary principals may be related to institutional maturity, professional autonomy, or organizational stability at this level.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that while certain organizational and psychological variables differ across school levels—particularly crime and violence, workload stress, academic pressure, and job satisfaction—school climate perceptions remain consistent. These results underscore the importance of adopting level-sensitive leadership policies and support mechanisms while recognizing the shared managerial commitment to sustaining positive educational environments across all school levels.

Ethics Committee Approval: This study was conducted using secondary data obtained from the publicly available TALIS 2018 dataset administered by the OECD. Since the data are anonymized and publicly accessible, and no direct interaction with human participants was involved, ethics committee approval was not required.

Author Contributions: The first author contributed approximately 60% to the conceptualization, data analysis, and writing of the manuscript, whereas the second author contributed approximately 40% to the study design, supervision, interpretation of findings, and manuscript revision.

Use of Artificial Intelligence: Artificial intelligence tools were not used in the design, data analysis, or interpretation stages of this study. AI-based tools were used solely for language editing and proofreading purposes.

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